

**TECHNOLOGY-MEDIATED LESSON STUDY.A STEP -BY-STEP
GUIDE.**

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the integration of technology into educational environments, specifically focusing on its benefits and challenges in the classroom. Despite the familiarity students have with technology, many schools still rely on analog tools. By discussing the potential benefits of using technology, such as increasing student engagement and providing immediate feedback, as well as the barriers to implementing technology, such as financial constraints and hardware limitations, this paper aims to provide insight into how teachers and students can benefit from incorporating technology into the classroom.

Keywords : Technology, classroom, education, student engagement, feedback, barriers, benefits, challenges, instructional design, active learning, organization, accessibility, costs

INTRODUCTION

Technology is at the center of our lives in most environments, and the classroom is no exception. Student in today's classrooms have grown up in a world surrounded by technology. They do not know what it is like to experience life without cell phones, computers, televisions and other common tech devices.

Despite this familiarity with technology, educational environments may be slow to integrate technology into the classroom. Many schools still use analog tools, such as books, notebooks, whiteboards and posters in instructional design. This could be attributed to lack of funding. However, some school districts have invested in instructional technology for the classroom by securing grant funding or donations from community and business partners. This includes smart boards to replace outdated projectors as well as personal digital devices such as iPads

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or Chromebooks. Technology has the potential to make aspects of education easier and more equitable in many ways. Let's find out how teachers and students can benefit from additional technology in the classroom.

Technology can assist with active learning sessions in the classroom to increase student engagement with a subject and provide immediate and meaningful feedback, and it can be used to either clarify new concepts or review previously taught material. It can assist the faculty member or preceptor with organization of materials and assignments, timestamp submission of projects or assignments, be linked to course management systems, including gradebooks, and be used for reflection and metacognition activities. Barriers include finding the time for both the presenter/preceptor and student to learn the systems employed, the financial impacts on both parties, computer and device hardware limitations, including battery life, and Internet connectivity issues. This paper, rather than focusing on individual software programs, focuses on general concepts to be considered when incorporating technology into a classroom or an experiential setting and discusses both the benefits and challenges of the technology. Specifically, the purpose and use of technology, equipment, accessibility, time, and costs are discussed.

Figure 1.

(a) In traditional lesson study, a teacher is observed by group members in the same classroom, followed by an in-person meeting, (b) In technology-mediated lesson study, the lesson is recorded, uploaded and reviewed asynchronously by group members, followed by a virtual meeting.

BENEFITS. One of the many benefits of using technology in the classroom is its ability to support personalized learning. Many platforms and applications accommodate different learning styles and abilities, making it easy for students to work at their own pace on a level that is unique to their needs. It

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also enables educators the ability to tailor their lessons to meet the diverse needs of all of their students. This approach is great for teachers because it gives them the time to work individually with students who may be struggling. Utilizing technology in this way ensures that all students have the opportunity to thrive and succeed.

It is worth mentioning that every school or university has technical rooms. Let's think about why these rooms are decorated with different colors. the only reason for this is that different colors have the ability to attract people, and if the lesson starts with different methods and interesting game technologies, it is very memorable and we try to learn something for ourselves. and a lesson that begins with attractive colors cannot force the student to think about anything but the lesson. Only if the lesson is always interesting and meaningful, every student can master the subject and the subject well. We know that it is difficult to imagine today without technology, so technology can be used effectively in every lesson.

First, adding technology to an activity or course should have a clear purpose; it should not be added only to say that technology is being used. Second, it is vital to determine how the teacher and the students will use the technology. The use and manageability of the software program are one of the most important aspects to consider when selecting technology to incorporate into the classroom or experiential setting. The software program capabilities should match the needs for the learning outcome. Technology should allow for student participation, thus engaging them in the teaching session. Learning should be fun! Technology can assist with activities and assessments in the class or course or fully become your active learning activities in class. Students can be introduced to material through software programs, or programs may be used to reinforce or apply concepts students learned previously. Identifying the purpose of the technology for the learning activity is key to selecting the ideal software program.

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CONCLUSION

Technology allows students to connect with the global community. Through video conferencing, digital group projects, and online forums and chats, students can learn from others from across the globe, unlike in a traditional classroom setting. These global connections allow students to see other perspectives, understand different cultures, and learn to communicate with others. This way of learning can be a very enriching experience and prepare students to work with others from all over the world in the future.

Technology changes by the minute, and as educators, it's critical to keep up with the times in order to best prepare our students for the constant shift in technology. Although integrating technology into the classroom has its benefits, it's important to note that traditional learning processes are just as essential. Take time to understand every aspect of educational technology that you will incorporate into your classroom. By doing so, you will find that technology can have a profound impact on students' learning experiences. The value of the instructor has never been higher. The value of learning guides, processes, and tools has never been higher. Teachers have sought hidden keys inside their students for hundreds of years to help them unlock knowledge, information, and wisdom. Students can now discover these keys for themselves, and instructors can act more as a guide and counsel and serve to challenge, motivate, and grow.

The science of learning continues to point towards effective learning pedagogies and tools for communicating and instruction. Like almost every other endeavor in life, education, and learning have only become more complex during

the pandemic as we face the continuing reality that learning is as much web-based as in-person.

We believe the best learning comes through planned interaction combined with facilitating exposure to information, technologies, tools, patterns, and relationships to help create awareness, skills, and competency.

Many students articulated that course attributes in the LMS and technologies used by their instructors helped provide clarity and structure, effective and flexible content delivery, clear communication, and a sense of belonging in a community. Yet for others, especially new and first-generation college students, going online was overwhelming. They felt as though a firehose of information was turned on, and this only increased their cognitive and psychological load. Still, we feel as though we have learned a great deal about best practices for supporting students' academic success. This perspective identifies approaches identified during ERT that instructors should either start, stop, or continue as instructors return to in-person instruction or find themselves continuing to teach online, in a hybrid format, or via hybrid flexible course formats. While these suggestions reflect our current research and understanding, they are necessarily limited to our institution's study population.

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